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D7.9: Dissemination Report III

WP7 – Exploitation and Communication

Authors: Nefeli POLITI-STERGIOU (EVF), Dimitri PAPADAKIS (EVF), Stefka Domuzova (EVF), Lefteris MAMAIS (EVF)

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Lead Author	Nefeli Politi-Stergiou (EVF)	Email	nefeli@evenflowconsulting.eu	
	Evenflow SPRL	Phone	+32 494 44 81 07	
Other authors	Stefka Domuzova (EVF), Dimitri Papadakis (EVF) and Eleftherios Mamais (EVF)			
Contributions from	All partners			
Reviewer(s)	Polimachi Simeonidou (DRAXIS), Dimitra Perperidou (DRAXIS)			
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Executive summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to **provide a comprehensive overview** of the dissemination, communication and marketing tools and activities developed during M18 – M34 of the APOLLO project. The overall objective of the dissemination and communication activities is to promote the results and benefits of the project to a range of relevant target audiences, in order to foster a sustainable customer base for the commercial service.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during this period include:

- maintaining APOLLO's website and social media account, which provide platforms for communicating APOLLO and disseminating news and material related to APOLLO to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the APOLLO services;
- APOLLO's newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination tools used and distributed at external conferences (such as the APOLLO brochure and leaflet and audience-focused presentations);
- creation of a strong commercial brand to commercialise the APOLLO services. The brand will underpin all marketing activities and promote user uptake.
- representation in media and conferences as well as the submission of scientific papers, enhancing APOLLO's visibility at national and international level to attract users, and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level.

During these months the scope of media presence and networking activities was to inform new target audiences and increase awareness to potential users regarding the APOLLO services as well as engaging them to become trial users. In parallel, the commercial brand and promotional materials were developed in order to maximise the effectiveness of moving to the commercial phase. To this end the APOLLO partners increased networking activities, focusing more on the APOLLO's services and results aiming among others to engage new users and at the fostering of closer scientific and technological cooperation between them and other academic, industrial and governmental partners in the field of Agriculture and Earth Observation services/applications, focused primarily on Europe.

This document provides short descriptions of the dissemination and communication activities reported from APOLLO partners, and carried out directly by the WP7 team. These include participation in conferences, networking events, media, publications etc. The positive impacts of these activities are already being felt, as exemplified by the requests for signing up as trial users either in the pilot regions or in other EU countries for more information about the services and requests from interested parties for potential cooperation.

1 Communication activities and tools

1.1 Brand identity

The APOLLO consortium intended to adopt a more commercial name before entering the market. To this end, APOLLO has built an integrated and coherent visual identity aiming to form the basis for a strong commercial brand as established in M1 and 2 of the project (and extensively described in the first document of this series “*D7.1 Dissemination, Communication and Marketing Plan I*”) the project’s visual identity consisted of the logo, colour pallet, and additional visual elements which work together to form a coherent and recognisable whole (e.g. service icons).

To find the most suitable name to commercialise its services, the APOLLO team took under consideration APOLLO’s overall value proposition for all users along with its features. It has been assessed that the commercial name needed to be based in the following elements:

- Easy to say and to remember in all languages
- Marketable
- Preferably exploit APOLLO’s well established visual identity and current “branding”

The consortium has first concluded to the name “FARMORE”, as described in the deliverable *D7.2 Dissemination, Communication and Marketing Plan II*. Although the Communications team had developed the new logo based on that name and prepared all the relevant materials accordingly, finally the name was turned down due to trademark risk. The name FARMORE is trademarked by another provider of agricultural services. However, when the initial due diligence was conducted, this wasn’t considered to be a major risk, as the trademarked product focuses on a different agricultural industry. As also explained in detail in the *3rd APOLLO Technical Report*, in order to ensure avoiding trademark infringement claim, a re-examination of the trademark issue for the name FARMORE was conducted and legal advice was obtained on how to proceed. Following the results, it was decided that the risk of a trademark infringement claim was too great to remain with the currently selected name. The team therefore proposed a set of alternatives, from which the final name was selected: “FARMINTEL”. The figure below presents all the elements FARMINTEL demonstrates making it the best choice for APOLLO’s commercialisation.

Figure 1: FARMINTEL logo concept description in a nutshell.

APOLLO's commercial product will be branded under FARMINTEL carrying all the elements of the visual identity of the project.

Figure 2: FARMINTEL logo.

"FARMINTEL", is currently free from any kind of trademarking claims and the consortium aims to proceed in order to ensure the name will be trademarked.

All the dissemination materials were updated and/or designed to reflect the FARMINTEL brand. In order to do this transition smoothly and keep the APOLLO's positive impressions to the existing networks, the phrase "*Powered by <APOLLO logo>*" is used to all "new" material.

1.2 Commercial mini-site

The commercial mini site is now available on line. The commercial mini site introduces APOLLO's commercial identity, present APOLLO as a product and overall it completes APOLLO's first promotional phase. The mini-site serves now as the primary online marketing tool. APOLLO has now moved forward from a project-based website to an attractive gateway hosting FARMINTEL's brand in order to communicate with potential customers and sell the FARMINTEL services. Currently the website provides all the important FARMINTEL features and is developed in such a way to provide the most important information to the visitor and to engage him to try the services. At the moment the website is directly linked to the APOLLO website where a visitor can find more details on the services, and the concept of the product. However, the FARMINTEL will become independent and all the relevant information will be on further developed on this site which will be hosted in the following domain: www.farmintel.app.

Figure 3: FARMINTEL mini-site, February 2019.

Expected Impact: As the website is online only for a short period of time, safer estimations will be made in a three-month period, also after having run strong promotional campaigns via the social media and by distributing the Press Releases. Potential customers will be able to download and purchase FARMINTEL through the portal.

1.3 Website

The APOLLO website (www.apollo-h2020.eu) currently serves as a supporting online tool for the commercial website of the FARMINTEL portal. The website was updated with the two new FARMINTEL services and it provides detailed information about the APOLLO project and the commercial services.

1.3.1 APOLLO project website statistics

The APOLLO website was put online on the 29th of August 2016, and officially launched in September (M05). Data on website traffic since then have been monitored using Google Analytics. The major statistic indicators are the following:

- **Sessions:** Session is defined as a group of interactions taken by one user within a given time frame (30 minutes) on the website. The number of sessions is an indicator of how many times the site has been visited.
- **Users:** Visitors that have had at least one session within the selected date range (includes both new and returning visitors).
- **Page views:** the total number of times a page has been viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Pages/Session:** average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- **Average Session Duration:** Average time spent by visitors browsing the site.
- **Bounce Rate:** the percentage of single-page visits (i.e. visits in which the visitor enters and leaves the site from the same page, without interacting with the rest of the site).
- Percentage of **New Sessions:** estimate of the percentage of first-time visitors.

The values of the above indicators for all users¹ are recorded in the following table, Table 1.

Indicator	Value	Value	Final Value
	(M06*-M18)	(M18-M34)	(M06-M34)
	<i>*Marks the launch of the website</i>		
Sessions	2762	3943	6705
Users	1620	2947	4567
New users (M06-M12)	720	1033	1753
Page views	7529	7894	15.423
Pages/Session	2.73	2.00	-
Average Session Duration	00:03:04 (h:m:s)	00:01:58	-
Bounce Rate	50.43%	63.5%	-

Table 1: Statistical indicators for the APOLLO website.

Sessions

Since launching, the APOLLO website has received 2762 visits (sessions) from 1620 users. As can be seen in Figure 4, immediately following the publication of the Newsletters, APOLLO increased the number of its visitors. Visits seem to have stabilised, with a few noticeable peaks occurring as a consequence of various other activities like media presence.

¹ In the first version of this deliverable, a segmentation of users was applied in order to remove the influence of automated web “crawlers” on the data, by counting only sessions longer than 30 seconds. Due to the limitations of Google Analytics when such segmentation is applied (90-day period only), we have been obliged to remove the filter. As such, the results now represent “all users”, which may include some non-human actors.

Figure 4: Visitor sessions for the APOLLO website and events participation (M18-M34).

As evident in Figure 5, 87.3% of total visitors to the website were new.

Figure 5: New and returning visitors (M18-M34).

Geolocation statistics

As can be seen in Figure 6 and Figure 7 **Error! Reference source not found.**, the majority of visits came from three countries: Greece (18.90% of the total sessions), Serbia (11.01% of the total sessions), Spain (8.39% of the total sessions) reflecting the pilot countries.

Sessions by country

1 Oct 2017 – 14 Feb 2019 ▾ [LOCATION OVER](#)

Figure 6: Overview of visits based on country of origin (M18-M34).

Looking closer at the statistics the next on the list is the USA with a noteworthy 7.79%. Belgium visitors represented 4.09% of total sessions. A noticeable number of visits came from other European countries; France 3.89% and Italy 3.86% as well as Germany and UK.

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Country	Users	% Users
1. Greece	568	18.90%
2. Serbia	331	11.01%
3. Spain	252	8.39%
4. United States	234	7.79%
5. Belgium	123	4.09%
6. France	117	3.89%
7. Italy	116	3.86%
8. India	93	3.09%
9. Germany	84	2.80%
10. United Kingdom	81	2.70%

Figure 7: Visits based on country of origin (M18-M34).

Users Flow statistics

To better understand the bounce rate and to better understand what triggered the users to visit the website and how they have interacted with it, we analysed the User Flow statistics. User Flow shows how the users have interacted with the website and the steps in each interaction. Analysing the Users flow based on Event action as well as based on country it is evident that most users either first visit the APOLLO’s frontpage or to a specific news article. The next interaction is usually the project page, the concept or change to another language.

Figure 8: User Flow per event action (M18-M34).

Country statistics show that the users coming from the pilot countries have first visited an article and browsed to learn more about the project. The contact page was also visited during the first interaction.

Figure 9: User Flow per country of origin (M18-M34).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to reach 5000 visitors to the APOLLO webpage. During M18-34 the APOLLO website attracted more than 1000 new users resulting in a total of 1753 for the period that the website has been published online. This is a result of the participation of all partners in dissemination and well-placed communication activities. The number of returning visitors is assumed to reflect the project partners and other users interested to be informed on the APOLLO updates. Statistics from user flow per country showed that the APOLLO news attracted much attention mostly from the pilot countries while visitors from other countries mostly interacted with the “project” and front page. Based on the dissemination and communication activities that took place during this reporting period, it can be assumed that new visitors are mainly farmers and agricultural consultants as well as other stakeholders interested in learning more about the APOLLO project, coming from the growing network of contacts established via activities such as conferences, media appearances and publications. The fact that APOLLO attracted many farmers expressing their interest to try the APOLLO services (either through the sign-up form or by contacting with the pilot national contacts) is amongst others reflected by the way users have interacted with the web site. The team expects to see further impacts once some first analytics from the APOLLO commercial site (FARMINTEL website) will be available.

1.4 Newsletter

During M18-M34, news and articles were published through the APOLLO website and promoted via APOLLO’s social media. However, after the entry into force of the GDPR, it proved difficult to retain the newsletter’s subscribers, and the decision was taken to focus on other ways of communicating with potential users. A final Newsletter is scheduled to be published late in M34 presenting APOLLO’s commercial product and announcing the conclusion of the project.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attract 3000 subscribers. However, the impact of the GDPR on the project’s subscribers was strongly felt. Almost all of the original subscribers were lost as a result of the failure to re-subscribe after the GDPR entered into force. As a mitigating measure, emphasis was placed on the use of social media to locate and engage followers.

1.4.1 Privacy policy and GDPR implementation

The GDPR came into force in May 2018, introducing a major reform in the field of privacy. Its aim is to increase the level of control of individuals over their personal data by simplifying the existent regulatory framework. All the partners of the APOLLO project subscribe to this Privacy Policy, and have acted in accordance with it in regard to procedures requiring collection and handling of personal data. As attested by the “privacy policy” section on the APOLLO website and in the relevant notice on the newsletter’s subscription page, users can readily access information on both the collection, and the consecutive treatment of their personal data – as well as opt out of certain activities – in line with the GDPR prescriptions.

1.5 APOLLO on Social Media

Both Facebook and Twitter were maintained to augment and complement the website as the central channel of stakeholders and potential customer engagement. Both channels were used as multiplier tools to promote the APOLLO news, and used to promote APOLLO news and events where the APOLLO partners had participated in and engage the audience to come and interact with the APOLLO representatives.

1.5.1 Twitter

Twitter was used with the goal to increase awareness and to further attract attention to the project and its services.

Figure 10: Screenshot from APOLLO’s Twitter profile page.

At the end of M06, the APOLLO Twitter account was following 101 other accounts related to the Agricultural sector (i.e. projects, private companies, agricultural professionals, EU agricultural institutions and decision makers) and was being followed by 23 other accounts. In M18 @APOLLO_Agri was following 213 accounts in total, related to the Agricultural and Remote sensing sectors, i.e. 112 more in twelve months, and was followed back by 130 accounts mainly related with

Agriculture, Remote sensing (including mainly decision makers, large organisations, academia, projects, scientists) and media. It is evident that APOLLO has increased its target audience by a factor of five over the course of a year. Currently, APOLLO has doubled its network and is followed by 234 followers including also more growers, agricultural cooperatives and related EU projects.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attract 50 followers. APOLLO Twitter has achieved triple the targeted value. During M18-M34, 103 more accounts have followed APOLLO reflecting the results of the dissemination and communication efforts from all partners. A solid network around APOLLO is being established and Twitter continues to be a very good tool to promote the project’s activities, news and attract more interest. During this period twitter was supported by and supporting all partner activities during project and third-party events. A twitter campaign has started in order to attract the interest for APOLLO’s commercial product that is about to be revealed. The FARMINTEL partners are considering the creation of a new Twitter account for FARMINTEL and promote it through the existing APOLLO account.

1.5.2 Facebook

APOLLO has established a Facebook page for the purpose of reaching out to groups and networks (such as Agri.EU - The Social Network of European Farmers) and for engaging in public conversations with a younger generation of technologically-aware farmers. The APOLLO Facebook page is currently being followed by 122 accounts and has been liked by 125 accounts. Both account groups are mostly individuals related to agriculture such as farmers, crop consultants, non-professional farmers, university students studying agri-related topics, etc. A strong Facebook campaign will follow in M34 as a marketing tool to promote FARMINTEL platform and services.

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to achieve 300 page “likes”. As indicated above, currently (M34) APOLLO has received 122 “likes”. People seem interested to interact with APOLLO. Facebook, like the other social channels will act as a multiplier to promote the new marketing material and to introduce FARMINTEL to the agri community and engage them.

1.6 Press Releases

During M18-M34, two Press Releases were created in order to inform the media and the market about the commercial name, the mini-site and the new services integrated in the FARMINTEL platform:

- A Press Release that presents APOLLO's commercial brand and the commercial mini-site.

- A Press Release announcing the two new services that APOLLO offers.

Both Press Releases will be translated in the partners languages and distributed through their channels and the APOLLO channels to national and international media.

Expected impact: The Press Releases will be used to amplify the promotion of the APOLLO commercial solution launch (FARMINTEL) through various channels in all pilot countries. This

expects to generate greater exposure for FARMINTEL and its services and reach wider audiences attracting their interest.

1.7 Press Kit

An updated press kit was developed aimed for circulation to journalists. FARMINTEL's Press Kit contains the two Press Releases for APOLLO's commercial product along with all the updated dissemination material for media, the new logo and FARMINTEL's contact point. The Press Kit will be available on the APOLLO website in the News and Media section.

Figure 11: FARMINTEL Press Kit information sheet.

1.8 Dissemination material

Dissemination tools were developed during the period M18-M34 in order to reflect the FARMINTEL brand. To this end, the existing material developed during the previous reporting period (see *D7.8 Communication and Dissemination Report II*) were updated, while four new documents were produced covering the FARMINTEL services' factsheets. The brochure and leaflet were updated in order to include the new services and rebranded under the FARMINTEL brand as presented in the following sections. This "new" customer-focused documents aim to be FARMINTEL's first promotional material for its commercial phase.

All materials are available both in printable and digital (web-ready) formats. Both the brochure and the leaflet are translated in three different languages, Serbian, Spanish and Greek.

1.8.1 Brochure

The APOLLO brochure was designed with the aim of providing a detailed overview of the benefits and advantages of the APOLLO services, with a view to creating brand awareness and attracting new customers.

Figure 12: FARMINTEL powered by APOLLO brochure (February 2019).

1.8.2 Leaflet

The APOLLO leaflet was designed with the aim of attracting the attention of target audiences with a small number of key messages, triggering brand awareness and encouraging visitors to the website and other social media.

Figure 13: FARMINTEL powered by APOLLO leaflet (February 2019).

1.8.3 Fact Sheets

Four factsheets were produced each of them outlining the benefits of the FARMINTEL services: Tillage Scheduling, Irrigation Scheduling, Crop Growth Monitoring and Crop Yield Estimation. It was decided that the Weather forecast and alerts service and the Management Zoning service, are better to be include in the Irrigation and Tillage factsheet, and Crop Growth Monitoring factsheet respectively as they are properly components of these services. The factsheets are designed to be a 2-pager promotional product providing useful information about each service such as the overall issue that the service addresses, service features and outputs. Each factsheet is divided in sections. The first page is a general presentation of each service highlighting its unique key features and actionable information. The first page aims to attract the reader to learn more about the service and attract attention. On the other hand, the second page provides insights on the technical aspects i.e “How it works” and what inputs are used to deliver the final outputs whilst highlighting the output maps that the user gets for his/her crop from the FARMINTEL platform. The final section contains the information about the output delivery methods as well as the FARMINTEL contact details.

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Figure 14: FARMINTEL powered by APOLLO factsheets (February 2019).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to distribute 2500 copies of the printed communication material. The “new” materials are currently available but since they are intended to be used for the commercial phase they were finalised in the last months of the project. Therefore, in this paragraph we will summarise the dissemination of the APOLLO brochure and leaflet which were used by the partners in several occasions. During M18-M34, more than 800 copies of leaflets and brochures were distributed in major agricultural events and info sessions from the APOLLO representatives by consortium partners (see Table 2). Compared to the previous period the amount of disseminated material has increased by a factor of four times reflecting the efforts of the APOLLO promotion in the pilot countries and at international scale.

1.9 FARMINTEL marketing tools

1.9.1 FARMINTEL pitch

During the reporting period a set of slides serving as a **sales pitch** to interested customers was created. The pitch is customer-driven and is primarily addressed to farmers. To this end, the language used is every day, simple language avoiding complex technical terms. It follows a story telling narrative and it aims to be appealing in both the senses of vision and hearing leading to a strong result. The pitch starts with a beginning phrase reflecting the best information about the key benefits of the product and continues comprises of six sections:

- Problem/challenge statement
- The solution/the service
- How it works and what it offers
- Farmers' experience
- The team behind the product
- Call to action

The Figure below shows some typical slides of the FARMINTEL pitch presentation.

Figure 15: Slides from the FARMINTEL pitch presentation.

1.9.2 FARMINTEL demo

The development of a **demonstration screencast** was supported by means of the production of a script and scene plan. The demo follows a pitch like narrative, using simple language and concrete messages that highlight the services benefits and shows how easy is to use the FARMINTEL platform and get the results.

2 Dissemination activities

Representatives from all APOLLO project partners have promoted the project using the means and channels at their disposal.

2.1 Conferences

A strategic campaign of event and conference attendance was planned for the lifetime of the APOLLO project and is registered in “D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan”. The aim is to maximise the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders, present the APOLLO solution as part of the programme of speakers and to distribute APOLLO marketing material to attendees. Dedicated presentations were produced by the participating partners to facilitate the promotion of APOLLO in the context of each event. The dedicated [Dissemination Report form²](#) was used to collect reports from partners on the activities in which they have been involved (See Annex I).

2.1.1 Third party conferences, events and workshops

Table 2 summarises the events at which APOLLO was represented, totalling twelve conferences, trade fairs and workshops.

Event	Description	APOLLO's involvement
AGRITECHNICA Hannover, Germany, 12-18 Nov 2017 Participation: AGRISAT No. of attendees: >450.000	Agritechnica is the world's leading exhibition for agricultural machinery and equipment.	Agrisat collected insights the state of the art and the actual situation of the companies' technologies, to be able to provide advanced technological solutions to the APOLLO platform.
Agro Expo 2018 Badajoz, Spain, 25-26 Jan 2018 Participation: AGRISAT No. of attendees: N/A	Agroexpo is an international tradefair taking place each year in Spain. It brings together farmers, manufacturers, distributors and agricultural professionals.	Cooperation Stand Abona Global at Agro Expo. AgriSat representatives gave an oral presentation to farmers about APOLLO, its services and its benefits.
Copernicus for Agricultural Applications Workshop DG GROW, Brussels (Belgium), 5 Feb 2018 Participation: AGRISAT, DRAXIS and EVF	The aim of the workshop is to address the possible role of the private (downstream) sector for possible solutions, integrating Copernicus data and Copernicus services' information, in support of the agricultural end-users at the different levels: international, European and Member States' level.	APOLLO was selected among as one of the three most important Horizon 2020 land downstream projects and was presented by the Research Executive Agency during the Copernicus for Agriculture workshop. This high-level event aimed to address the possible role of the private (downstream) sector for solutions in support of the agricultural end-users at international, European

² A preview of the Google form can be found in Annex I.

<p>No. of attendees: >50</p>		<p>and Member State level. APOLLO representatives got the opportunity to exchange with other agri-professionals who have started with funding from EU projects and currently run successful businesses or start-ups in the sector. Also, the APOLLO representatives got the opportunity to learn more about the latest advancements on EU regulations, EU policies and the challenges that are critical for the EU for Agriculture.</p> <p>More than 100 APOLLO brochures were distributed.</p>
<p>PIONEER Workshop Leon, Spain, 30 Nov 2017</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT No. of attendees: 100</p>	<p>A workshop mostly dedicated in agricultural industry machinery</p>	<p>AgriSat delivered an oral presentation demonstrating the variable rate of sowing based on AgriSat maps. APOLLO could be used to monitor the growing crops.</p>
<p>FIMA 2018. 40th International Fair of Agricultural machinery Zaragoza, Spain, 19-24 Nov 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT No. of attendees: 1572</p>	<p>The fair brought together farmers and companies linked with the agricultural sector. Innovation agri-machinery from Spain and other countries. Several technical sessions, professional meetings and trade missions have taken place.</p>	<p>AgriSat was an exhibitor in FIMA. An oral presentation and a rollup were used to promote the project's results. Attendees showed great interest for the APOLLO platform and how it works. APOLLO representatives explained the technology and benefits of the project. Other corporate material that included APOLLO were distributed.</p>
<p>III Simposio Nacional de Ingeniería Hortícola Lugo, Spain, 5 Apr 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT No. of attendees: >2000</p>	<p>The event brought together researchers and farmers to discuss about the 'Use of drones and satellites in agriculture'. About 100 Spanish and Portuguese researchers addressed the theme for the wide range of possibilities in R&D that represent these new</p>	<p>A poster and an article were presented by the APOLLO representatives. Calculation of net water needs in garlic and onion throughout the cultivation cycle using remote sensing tools including the APOLLO technology in the province of Albacete.</p>

	technologies for the agricultural sector.	
<p>XIV Congreso Nacional de Comunidades de Regantes de España</p> <p>Torre Vieja, Spain, 7 Apr 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~1000</p>	<p>This Congress is a meeting point and a space for analysis on the main concerns that affect the national irrigation sector. Congress participants were mostly water user associations and farmers.</p>	<p>AgriSat networked with various irrigators and distributed APOLLO leaflets and brochures.</p>
<p>Flagship Conference Food 2030</p> <p>Plovdiv, Bulgaria, 14-15 Jun 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT</p> <p>No. of attendees: N/A</p>	<p>Food 2030 is an international fair focused on the models to understand drivers of sustainable food consumption and adapt these to climate, agricultural, resource circularity and efficiency, and other societal challenges, the Flagship Conference Food 2030 will try to identify novel approaches and tools to address these challenges and contribute to consolidate around models to bridge health and sustainability. The event brought together participants from the EU Member States, i.e. high level officials, industry, entrepreneurs, investors, policy makers, and civil society organisations.</p>	<p>AgriSat was an exhibitor in that conference. In AgriSat's stand, attendees got the opportunity to learn more about the services' benefits, the pilots, the latest results. Besides the one-on-one discussions a roll up, APOLLO leaflet and brochure were used to promote the project. AgriSat also gave an oral presentation about the project's results.</p>
<p>GFIA Europe. Global Forum for Innovations in Agriculture.</p> <p>Utrecht, Netherlands, 20 - 21 Jun 2018</p> <p>Participation : AGRISAT</p> <p>No. of attendees: 2600</p>	<p>The Global Forum for Innovations in Agriculture has emerged as a global authority on sustainable food production, driving innovation through exhibitions and conferences across the world. Since 2014, GFIA events have welcomed over 25,000 visitors and worked with over 50 globally significant partners committed to using the Forum as a catalyst for change.</p>	<p>APOLLO representatives had the opportunity to exchange with researchers and network with professionals in the agricultural sector.</p>

<p>14th ICPA International Conference on Precision Agriculture Montreal, Canada, 24-27 Jul 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT</p> <p>No. of attendees: 470</p>	<p>Organised by the International Society of Precision Agriculture (ISPA) which is a non-profit professional scientific organization.</p>	<p>AgriSat representatives had the chance to network and present the APOLLO services to crop consultants and agribusiness people. Leaflets and brochures were also distributed.</p>
<p>InfoAg2018 St.Louis, Missouri (US), 23-25 Jul 2018</p> <p>Participation: AGRISAT</p> <p>No. of attendees: ~1600</p>	<p>Since 1995, the InfoAg Conference has been the premier event for discussion and advancement of precision agriculture. This event draws interest from domestic and international agriculture professionals and features a wide range of educational and networking opportunities for professionals interested in learning more about precision agriculture techniques.</p>	<p>AgriSat participated in InfoAg for the second year. AgriSat representatives had the chance to network with crop consultants and agribusiness people. APOLLO leaflets and brochures were also distributed.</p>
<p>Conference on Big Data from Space - BiDS'17 Toulouse, France, 28 - 30 Nov 2017</p> <p>Participation: TUW</p> <p>No. of attendees: >50</p>	<p>BiDS'17 was co-organised by the European Space Agency (ESA), the Joint Research Center of the European Commission (JRC), and the European Union Satellite Centre (SatCen) and hosted by CNES, the French Government Space Agency.</p>	<p>TUW representatives had presented the APOLLO scientific results during bilateral discussions with peers.</p>
<p>Tallinn Space Week, 3-9 November, Tallinn, Estonia</p> <p>Participation: DRAXIS</p> <p>No. of attendees: N/A</p>	<p>The Tallinn Space Week, held under the auspices of the 2017 Estonian Presidency of the Council of the European Union Team was a week dedicated to the EU space sector and the related EU projects.</p>	<p>The APOLLO consortium was invited to present the project as a Horizon 2020 example of best practice at the Tallinn Space Week. APOLLO's Senior Scientific Expert, Dr Stelios Kotsopoulos, presented the project, highlighting how it aims to bring the benefits of space technology to small and large farms in order to help them improve their agricultural and financial resources.</p>
<p>XXX. International Horticultural Congress, 12-16 Aug 2018, Istanbul, Turkey</p>	<p>The 30th IHC attracted almost 1800 delegates from more than 90 countries. The program featured 9 plenary lectures, 67 keynote speakers,</p>	<p>APOLLO's Senior Scientific Advisor, Dr. Spyros Fountas, presented the APOLLO project</p>

Participation: AUA No. of attendees: >2500	more than 950 oral and 750 poster presentations in the opening session, 2 Colloquia, 39 (24 within the ISHS series) symposia and 11 workshops.	and its benefits to the farm processes.
IGARSS 2018, 22-27 Jul 2018, Valencia, Spain Participation: Starlab No. of attendees: N/A	The 38th annual symposium of the IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Society (GRSS). The theme for this year's conference highlights the pressing demands for "Observing, Understanding And Forecasting The Dynamics Of Our Planet".	Starlab partners disseminated the results of the calibration of the APOLLO soil moisture service to the scientific community.

Table 2: Conferences and workshops at which APOLLO was represented (M18-M34).

2.1.1 Partners' organised events

Table 3 summarises the events which APOLLO partners had organised and presented APOLLO.

Event	Description	APOLLO's involvement
Meeting to present the EU Incentives for Agriculture (IPARD) to farmers. Agriculture advisory service in Ruma Ruma, Serbia, 18 Jan 2018 Organisation: UPOR No. of attendees: 45	The Agriculture advisory service in Ruma organised a meeting to present the EU Incentives for Agriculture (IPARD) to farmers. Farmers and agricultural consultants from Ruma have participated.	Farmers and consultants showed a strong interest about the APOLLO project and the services. UPOR representatives answered their questions and distributed leaflets and brochures.
Meeting with farmers about the incentives of the Provincial Secretariat for Agriculture of A-P Vojvodina in Ruma. Ruma, Serbia, 28 Apr 2018 Organisation: UPOR No. of attendees: ~110	Meeting with farmers about the incentives of the Provincial Secretariat for Agriculture of AP Vojvodina in Ruma.	UPOR representatives introduced the APOLLO project and its benefits to farmers.
High agricultural school "Stevan Petrović Brile" Ruma, Serbia, 30 Nov 2017 Organisation: UPOR	Meeting with farmers about incentives for agriculture and their relationship to the introduction of standards.	UPOR representatives introduced the APOLLO project and its benefits to farmers.

No. of attendees: ~110		
Interview, Albacete, Spain Organisation: AgriSat No. of attendees: 4	A bilateral meeting with potential APOLLO users took place.	AgriSat gave a presentation and web platform demonstration. Attendees were very interested in the APOLLO platform.

Table 3: Conferences and workshops at which APOLLO was represented (M18-M34).

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to attend 15 events. APOLLO representatives had already attended 20 events during the previous reporting periods, and, as indicated above, 13 events since (M18-M34), for a total of 32 events which is more than twice the targeted amount. APOLLO partners have strongly promoted APOLLO in various events and fairs with various audiences. In addition to international presence, much focus was also given in promoting APOLLO in the pilot countries. That resulted to many new leads and interested potential end users to all pilot countries. Each pilot is addressing the requests in coordination with the project coordinator.

2.2 Scientific publications

Publishing articles in qualified publications guarantees the effective dissemination of specific project results, targeting groups of experts in the sectors addressed by APOLLO. For this reason, a set of conferences and scientific journals were identified. In the scientific domain publishing results in peer-reviewed journals, and in peer-reviewed conferences is the dominant mechanism for knowledge transfer. During the reported period, one scientific paper by UBFCE, "*Spatio-temporal regression kriging model of mean daily temperature for Croatia*" submitted to the Theoretical and Applied Climatology journal.

2.3 Media

Since the start of the project on the 1st of May 2016, representatives of the consortium have promoted the project in the media, through regional TV interviews and articles in national news. Notably, throughout the period M18 to M34, APOLLO representatives have continued promoting the project in several occasions on both traditional and online media. The following subsections describe the activities held per country.

2.3.1 Serbia

- [Article](#) (RS) addressed to farmers and focused on APOLLO's numerous benefits. Published in a specialised agricultural website, 3 July 2018.
- [Article](#) (RS) presented APOLLO benefits for farmers. Published in a specialised agricultural website (in Serbian), 28 April 2018.
- [Article](#) (RS) engaging farmers to fill in a questionnaire providing their feedback about APOLLO and register to become trial users for free. Published in a specialised agricultural website, 26 November 2018.

2.3.2 Greece

- Article and interview (GR) presenting APOLLO and how its services have helped Traianos Terzis, APOLLO's pilot agricultural consultant, to improve the management of various crops and become more efficient. Published on Agrenda, a Greek paper journal focused on agriculture, July 2018.

Figure 16: APOLLO on the Greek paper agri-journal “Agrenda”, published in July 2018 (EN Title: “Precision irrigation, fertilisation and crop protection”).

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- [Article](#) presenting how satellites and robots can benefit agriculture, APOLLO is mentioned as a state-of-the-art project for Greece. Published in the national media Kathimerini, 4 February 2019.
- [Article](#) discussing the APOLLO benefits in agriculture. Published in local media, 6 February 2019.

2.3.3 International media

- [Article](#) entitled “*Helping small farmers to meet growing food needs*” presents the APOLLO project and its benefits to the EU small holder farmers. Published in EC’s website, January 2019 .

Impact/Progress: According to the key performance indicators defined in D7.1 “1st Dissemination, communication and marketing plan”, the overall target is to have 45 appearances in the media. During this reporting period APOLLO has appeared in 7 articles, radio/TV shows at national and international level, while 15 during the period M01-M17. These appearances had a major effect in engaging new people to get involved in APOLLO as shown from the other indicators above, especially starting from the second reporting period and continuing until the end of the project. APOLLO partners will continue promoting FARMINTEL activities through the media to attract more potential customers to the platform.

2.4 Actions with similar projects

APOLLO representatives have sought to establish contacts and exploit synergies with the following complementary initiatives, organisations and projects:

- DIANA (H2020 project): DRAXIS is coordinator of this project, and relevant synergies have been established internally.
- KATANA (H2020 project):
- CEJA: European Council of Young Farmers, representing the interests of young farmers at European level. Modern, market orientated and innovative agriculture.
- COCERAL: European association representing the trade in cereals, rice, feedstuffs, oilseeds, olive oil, oils and fats and agro-supply.
- IFOAM EU: Advocates for the development and integrity of organic food and farming in Europe, representing over 180 member organisations.
- COPA-COGECA: Association of farmers and agri-cooperatives in the EU, representing 23 million farmers, pressing for a strong agriculture sector.
- SUMP: Serbian Young Farmers Association.

3 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report has provided an overview of the dissemination, communication and marketing activities implemented in the scope of the APOLLO project, in accordance with the provisions of the Dissemination Plan “D7.1: Dissemination, communication and marketing plan” issued during the first months of the project (M03). The effectiveness of these activities has been ensured by defining appropriate target groups, allowing the most relevant audiences to be reached with the most appropriate dissemination and communication tools and activities. The main aim is to keep the interested parties engaged with the project and its results, with the ultimate intention of converting them into customers.

APOLLO continued to be represented in various events regionally, at European and international level. Participation in various events such as workshops, conferences and networking events were an important activity for expanding networks, creating partnerships, as well as promoting APOLLO. Partners have successfully embarked on building networks of contacts who are interested in the APOLLO services regionally and in the EU with the goal to convert them to customers and/or partners. On the other hand, participation in trade fairs and other technology focused events, has also allowed the enrichment of the market knowledge of the APOLLO partners. It has provided meaningful insights into the key competitors and their practices as well as it introduced APOLLO as an emerging solution and its components as possible opportunities for partnerships and/or paying licenced products. As a more traditional means and with a national reach, continuous presence in the media (TV, radio and press) through consortium representatives in the pilot countries has helped towards building a good impression about the brand and to increase interest in the wider audience whose sub group are agri professionals. In the pilot countries, partners reported that these activities led to many requests for involvement in the project and more specifically in interested potential trial users. In order to further inform regional potential users, the pilot partners have also organised several meet ups with farmers, agri consultants and cooperatives presenting APOLLO, demonstrating the platform and explaining the benefits.

Supported by the communication and dissemination tools, **the APOLLO partners have informed and generated interest amongst more than 3100 farmers, 800 agri consultants and 30 cooperatives during the three years of the project.** Partners reported that many of the informed attended showed keen interest in becoming trial users either through the Sign-up form - 69 potential trial users in all pilot and other countries, most of them being farmers and agri-consultants – and by expressing directly their interest to the pilot partners. A non-EU audience and the scientific community were also reached through the participation of APOLLO representatives in international conferences, as well as the publication of papers in specialised publications. Strong networks of stakeholders in both fields is a necessary and important step in the harmonisation of activities and efforts to maximise regional stakeholder’s awareness of APOLLO’s services.

During this last year APOLLO has built a solid brand to introduce its commercial product, FARMINTEL. As FARMINTEL replaces APOLLO, the Press Releases will maximise the communications’ impact at national and international level and are a critical tool to move on to the commercial phase. Furthermore, all the newest materials are underpinned by the commercial brand (FARMINTEL) and have a marketing driven design. In addition, the FARMINTEL mini site will be the main channel of introducing the FARMINTEL brand and is expected to maximise the customer engagement. The FARMINTEL demo and pitch are the two main marketing tools to attract potential users with the intention to gradually convert them to customers. APOLLO representatives were followed up in many cases after the events to provide more information about APOLLO and its technology.

4 Annexes

Annex I: APOLLO Dissemination Report

APOLLO Dissemination Report

May-October 2016

This form is for reporting APOLLO dissemination activities during the above time period. Please note that events should be reported using the Event Report template available in Dropbox\APOLLO\Templates.

* Απαιτείται

Διεύθυνση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου *

Η διεύθυνσή σας ηλεκτρονικού ταχυ...

Partner *

Επιλογή ▾

Activity type *

Επιλογή ▾

Date(s) and place of activity (if applicable)

Η απάντησή σας

Description of activity

Η απάντησή σας

Audience (size/demographics)

Η απάντησή σας

Key stakeholders

Η απάντησή σας

Feedback / impact

Η απάντησή σας

Promotional material used

Η απάντησή σας

Material produced (e.g. photos, videos, presentations etc.)

Η απάντησή σας

ΥΠΟΒΟΛΗ

Σελίδα 1 από 1

Μην υποβάλλετε ποτέ κωδικούς πρόσβασης μέσω των Φορμών Google.

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